

Studies in Quinoline Compounds. Part VI.

BY UPENDRANATH BRAHMACHARI AND JNANENDRA MOHAN DAS-GUPTA.

The first series of compounds investigated in the following paper are alkylaminoquinoline derivatives which bear close relationship to plasmquine type of compounds. The general contour is very similar; while position 8 is occupied by amino group, position 6 is occupied by a methoxy, ethoxy or chloro group. Further attachment of an alkylamino group to the former makes the general structure akin to that usually ascribed to plasmquine, the constitution of which, however, is not definitely known. The object of preparing these compounds is, therefore, to approach the constitution of plasmquine in a systematic way. The similarity of the compounds investigated with plasmquine will be apparent from the following structures.

It will be noticed that the alkylaminoquinolines prepared by us contain asymmetric carbon atoms which are also present in plasmquine and quinine.

The second series of compounds are characterised by having unsaturated linkages (attached to the amino group in position 8), which are also present in quinine though not in plasmquine.

In all cases the hydrochlorides have been prepared as these are more easily crystallised than the corresponding bases; moreover, the bases are insoluble in water while the hydrochlorides are readily soluble and are so well adapted for pharmacological experiments.

EXPERIMENTAL.

First Series.

6-Methoxy-8- β -aminoisopropylaminoquinoline Dihydrochloride.

The preparation of this compound is given here in greater detail than in our previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, **8**, 571). The starting materials for the synthesis of this compound are 6-methoxy-8-aminoquinoline and β -bromoisopropylphthalimide. The former is prepared by nitrating acetyl-*p*-anisidine and subsequent hydrolysis of the acetyl group.

The amino compound thus obtained is then subjected to Skraup's reaction which gives 6-methoxy-8-aminoquinoline (British Pat., 267, 169). This is then condensed with β -bromoisopropylphthalimide. This latter is obtained by condensing phthalic anhydride with allylamine and then warming the resulting allylphthalimide with fuming HBr or alternately by condensing allyliodide with potassium phthalimide and then proceeding as above (*cf. Seitz, Ber.*, 1891, **24**, 2624).

6-Methoxy-8-aminoquinoline (1 g.) and bromoisopropylphthalimide (2 g.) are boiled together in an oil-bath at 130° for about 6 hours at the end of which the mass solidifies. The product is then treated with alcohol which dissolves the excess of bromopropylphthalimide and aminoquinoline, while the hydrobromide of phthalimidoisopropylaminomethoxyquinoline remains insoluble. It is then filtered, washed with alcohol and dried. As it is difficult to hydrolyse it, its hydrazine condensation product is prepared, which can be easily hydrolysed (*cf. Ing and Muske, J. Chem. Soc.*, 1926, p. 2348).

The hydrobromide (5 g.) is treated with alcohol (3 c.c.) and hydrazine hydrate (0.1 c.c.) next added. The whole is refluxed for 1½ hours and alcohol is distilled off while a white spongy mass remains. This latter is then hydrolysed by warming for about 15 minutes on a water-bath with excess of dilute hydrochloric acid. The

mixture is filtered, the filtrate is made alkaline and the precipitated base is extracted with chloroform. The chloroform solution is then treated with HCl gas, when the dihydrochloride is obtained. This is purified from alcohol in yellow crystalline form melting at 218-20°. It readily dissolves in water to a clear yellow solution. (Found: N, 13.70; Cl, 23.30. $C_{13}H_{19}ON_3Cl_2$ requires N, 13.81; Cl, 23.35 per cent.).

2-Methyl-6-methoxy-8-β-aminoisopropylaminoquinoline Dihydrochloride.

It is obtained similarly from 2-methyl-6-methoxy-8-aminoquinoline which is prepared by applying Doebner and Miller's reaction to 4-methoxy-2-nitroaniline and subsequent reduction. It is a yellow crystalline compound which melts at 260°. (Found: N, 13.30; Cl, 22.20. $C_{14}H_{21}ON_3Cl_2$ requires N, 13.34; Cl, 22.33 per cent.).

2-Methyl-6-ethoxy-8-β-aminoisopropylaminoquinoline dihydrochloride.—It is obtained from 2-methyl-6-ethoxy-8-aminoquinoline which results from Doebner and Miller's reaction on the corresponding nitroaniline and subsequent reduction. It melts at 270°. (Found: N, 12.70; Cl, 21.42. $C_{15}H_{23}ON_3Cl_2$ requires N, 12.65; Cl, 21.38 per cent.).

6-Chloro-8-β-aminoisopropylaminoquinoline dihydrochloride.—It is obtained as before from 6-chloro-8-aminoquinoline. It is a yellow crystalline compound melting at 212°. (Found: N, 13.50; Cl, 34.41. $C_{12}H_{16}N_3Cl_3$ requires N, 13.61; Cl, 34.52 per cent.).

2-Methyl-6-chloro-8-β-aminoisopropylaminoquinoline dihydrochloride.—It is obtained as above from 2-methyl-6-chloro-8-aminoquinoline. It melts at 255°. (Found: N, 13.1; Cl, 33.1. $C_{13}H_{18}N_3Cl_3$ requires N, 13.02; Cl, 33.02 per cent.).

2-Methyl-8-β-aminoisopropylaminoquinoline dihydrochloride.—It is prepared similarly from 2-methyl-8-aminoquinoline. It melts at

275-80°. (Found: N, 14.50; Cl, 24.42. $C_{13}H_{10}N_3Cl_2$ requires N, 14.58; Cl, 24.65 per cent.).

Second Series.

Allylthiocarbamido-8-aminoquinoline Hydrochloride.

Aminoquinoline (1 g.) is mixed with allylisocyanate (1 g.) in methyl alcohol (5 c.c.). The mixture is warmed on water-bath for sometime and then poured into water. The precipitate is dissolved in hydrochloric acid, shaken with ether and the aqueous solution is made alkaline. The precipitate obtained is taken up with chloroform and the hydrochloride precipitated therefrom by passing HCl gas. It crystallises from alcohol and melts at 150°. It forms a yellow crystalline chromate with $K_2Cr_2O_7$ which does not melt below 300°. (Found: N, 15.20; Cl, 12.61. $C_{13}H_{14}N_3SCl$ requires N, 15.02; Cl, 12.70 per cent.).

Allyl-8-aminoquinoline Hydrochloride.

8-Aminoquinoline (1 g.) and allylbromide (1 g.) are mixed with Na_2CO_3 (2 g.) dissolved in 10 c.c. of water. The whole is refluxed for three hours. The mixture is shaken with ether and the hydrochloride is precipitated from the ethereal solution by passing HCl gas. It crystallises from alcohol, m.p. 175°. It gives with potassium dichromate solution a chromate which does not melt below 300°. (Found: N, 12.8; Cl, 11.50. $C_{12}H_{13}N_2Cl$ requires N, 12.7; Cl, 11.56 per cent.).

Allylthiocarbamido-8-amino-6-ethoxyquinoline Hydrochloride.

The starting materials in the preparation of this compound are 6-ethoxy-8-aminoquinoline and allylthiocyanate. The former is obtained by reducing 6-ethoxy-8-nitroquinoline with SnCl_2 and conc. HCl , the nitroquinoline derivative itself being obtained by applying Skraup's reaction to 4-ethoxy-2-nitroaniline (*loc. cit.*).

6-Ethoxy-8-aminoquinoline (2 g.) and an equivalent amount of allylthiocyanate in 10 c.c. of methyl alcohol are warmed together on water bath for about an hour. The mixture is poured into water and purified as in the case of allylthiocarbamido-8-aminoquinoline. The hydrochloride is produced by passing dry HCl gas through its ethereal solution. It melts at 160° and forms a yellow dichromate which does not melt below 300° . (Found: N, 13·10; Cl, 11·10; $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{18}\text{ON}_3\text{SCl}$ requires N, 12·98; Cl, 10·97 per cent.)

Allyl-8-amino-6-ethoxyquinoline Hydrochloride.

It is prepared by refluxing a mixture of 6-ethoxy-8-aminoquinoline (1 g.), allylbromide (1·1 g.) and Na_2CO_3 (2 g.) dissolved in 8—10 c.c. of water. The refluxing is continued for 2 to 3 hours. It is then cooled and treated with ether. The hydrochloride is prepared as in the case of allyl-8-aminoquinoline; m.p. 182° . It forms a crystalline dichromate, which does not melt below 300° . (Found: N, 10·58; Cl, 13·32. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{17}\text{ON}_2\text{Cl}$ requires N, 10·59; Cl, 13·42 per cent.)

N-(8-quinolyyl)- μ -Amino- α -methylthiazoline Hydrochloride.

It is prepared by warming allylthiocarbamido-8-aminoquinoline with excess of concentrated hydrobromic acid on water-bath for about an hour. The mixture is cooled and diluted with water and then made alkaline with caustic soda solution. The precipitate is next extracted with ether. The ethereal solution is dried over anhydrous K_2CO_3 , and the hydrochloride prepared as usual. It melts at $215-20^\circ$ (decomp.). It is a light yellow substance and dissolves with difficulty in water to a light yellow solution. (Found: N, 15.00; Cl, 12.62. $C_{13}H_{14}N_3SCl$ requires N, 15.02; Cl 12.70 per cent.).

THE BRAHMACHARI RESEARCH INSTITUTE,
82-3, CORNWALLIS STREET,
CALCUTTA.

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